

Title: Asymptotic Relativistic Force Field

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1. Introduction:-

To explain an unreachable object, paradoxes like Zeno's paradox are used (which tell us that you can divide space an infinite amount of times, making it so that it'll take infinite time to reach the location). But these paradoxes rely on flawed logic, and were proven wrong with the concept of limits and calculus. This paper demonstrates how I used calculus itself to build a kinematics model of this unreachable object, and how I used Einstein's general relativity to explain how this object actually is unreachable.

2. Kinematics:-

1. Linear decay:-

The velocity of the object v decreases linearly as the remaining displacement from the body ($0 \leq s \leq r$) gets smaller. Considering $v \propto -s$, we can get an equation for velocity.

Removing the proportionality symbol:-

$$v = -ks$$

Writing velocity in its differential form:-

$$\frac{ds}{dt} = -ks$$

Separating the variables:-

$$\frac{1}{-s} ds = k dt$$

Integrating both sides:-

$$\int \frac{1}{-s} ds = \int k dt$$

$$\begin{aligned} -\ln(s) + c_1 &= kt + c_2 \\ -\ln(s) &= kt + C \end{aligned}$$

$$\ln(s) = -kt - C$$

Exponentiate both sides with e :-

$$s = e^{-kt-C}$$

Separate the exponents:-

$$s = e^{-kt} e^{-C}$$

Considering the scenario that $t = 0$ where $s = r$:-

$$r = e^{-C}$$

Plug this into our original equation and we get:-

$$s = e^{-kt} r$$

Plug that into our original equation for v :-

$$v = -k e^{-kt} r$$

Now at $t = 0$, v is initial velocity (v_0), considering that:-

$$\begin{aligned} -v_0 &= -kr \\ k &= \frac{v_0}{r} \end{aligned}$$

So we get the equation:-

$$v = -\frac{sv_0}{r}$$

And for s the equation is:-

$$s = e^{-\frac{v_0}{r} t} r$$

If we plot this on a time graph with $v_0 = 1$ and $r = 1$, with a red line representing distance and a blue representing velocity. We get this:-

If we plot this on a distance graph:-

In both graphs you can observe that the velocity decays to 0, and the distance graph makes the linear decay even clearer. But the distance closes down rather quickly. So even though this linear decay might have some real world applications, for our purposes it's not the one.

2. Quadratic decay:-

So instead let's assume the velocity of the object (v) decays **quadratically** as $s \rightarrow 0$. So considering $v \propto -s^2$, we get:-

$$v = -ks^2$$

Solving for k , we get the equation:-

$$v = -\frac{v_0 s^2}{r^2}$$

And for s :-

$$s = \frac{r^2}{v_0 t + r}$$

If we plot this on a time graph and a distance graph (assuming $r = 1$ and $v_0 = 1$) we get:-

In the distance graph you can observe the quadratic decay of the velocity, and on the time graph you can observe how the distance closes down much slower compared to the linear decay. For example, it'll take you 13.82 seconds to reach 1 micrometer (10^{-6} m) with the linear decay, but 11.57 days using the quadratic decay. So for our purposes, the quadratic decay is superior and it'll be used going forward.

3. Relativity:-

With the kinematics we can explain how an object moves inside this field, but not how the field itself works or behaves. So we make the assumption that this field works like gravity, but instead of pulling objects together, it pushes them away. Einstein's theory of relativity (our current best theory of gravity) states that gravity works by distorting spacetime, creating a well which pulls objects in. So this force field must work by distorting spacetime to create a hill, pushing objects away.

How an object distorts space time is given by the Einstein field equation.

$$G_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu}$$

But this equation is actually a set of 10 interconnected differential equations. So instead of solving all of them, we are going to be using the Schwarzschild metric.

$$ds^2 = - \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right) c^2 dt^2 + \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right)^{-1} dr^2$$

Which is a solution of the field equation specifically for a point mass in an empty universe distorting flat spacetime, and it's also the equation used to find how gravity distorts space time. Let's simplify the multiples next to dt^2 and dr^2 to A and B :-

$$ds^2 = -Ac^2 dt^2 + Bdr^2$$

The values of A and B in the Schwarzschild metric are specifically derived for gravity. So for our repulsive field, we need to derive our own values.

First let's convert our velocity equation to spherical coordinates, which are used by this metric.

$$v = -\frac{v_0 r^2}{R^2}$$

Let's assume the movement of light where $ds^2 = 0$:-

$$0 = -Ac^2 dt^2 + Bdr^2$$

Separating the variables:-

$$-c\sqrt{\frac{A}{B}} = \left(\frac{dr}{dt}\right)$$

Plugging in our velocity equation for $\frac{dr}{dt}$:-

$$-c\sqrt{\frac{A}{B}} = -\frac{v_0 r^2}{R^2}$$

Now because we assumed the movement of light, the initial velocity should be c :-

$$-c\sqrt{\frac{A}{B}} = -\frac{cr^2}{R^2}$$

Separating variables:-

$$\frac{A}{B} = \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^4$$

In the Schwarzschild metric, B is just the reciprocal of A , if we assume that then:-

$$A^2 = \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^4$$

$$A = \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^2$$

Which means:-

$$B = \left(\frac{R}{r}\right)^2$$

If we plug this into our original equation, we get our very own metric for our force field.

$$ds^2 = -\left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^2 c^2 dt^2 + \left(\frac{R}{r}\right)^2 dr^2$$

From this we can see how the space warps and time dilates due to this field.

1. Time dilation:-

The relationship of the space time interval (ds^2) and proper time ($d\tau$) is given by:-

$$ds^2 = -c^2 d\tau^2$$

If we plug this into our metric (assuming no movement), we get:-

$$-c^2 d\tau^2 = -\left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^2 c^2 dt^2$$

$$cd\tau = \left(\frac{r}{R}\right) cdt$$

$$d\tau = \left(\frac{r}{R}\right) dt$$

If we plot this on a distance graph with $R = 1$ and assuming a time interval of 1, we get this:-

You can clearly observe that the radius (1) there is no time dilation, but as you get closer to the center from the radius, time slows down, until at the center where it stops.

2. Space warping:-

If we assume the time step (dt) to be 0, we get this equation from our metric:-

$$ds^2 = \left(\frac{R}{r}\right)^2 dr^2$$

We can take $ds = dl$, as we are only measuring space, and simplify to get:-

$$dl = \left(\frac{R}{r}\right) dr$$

If we plot this on a distance graph with $R = 1$ and a space interval of 1, we get this:-

Here too you can clearly observe that at the radius (1) space is essentially flat, but as you approach the center, the spatial distance spikes to infinity. Meaning that this field is warping space in such a way, that it creates infinite distance between the center and the radius.

4. Conclusion:-

The relativistic part of this paper tells us that the motion explained by the kinematics is merely an illusion to the outside observer. The field isn't pushing back or slowing anything down, it is creating infinite distance within finite space to prevent any object from ever reaching the center.